

DEVELOPING SPEAKING FLUENCY THROUGH TASK-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract

This paper investigates the efficacy of TBLT in improving speaking fluency through a range of communicative tasks. These tasks include collaborative projects, group discussions, and role-plays, which mimic real-world language use. The findings contribute to understanding how structured task design impacts learners' confidence and fluency over time.

Speaking fluency is a critical skill for second language learners, often considered the key to effective communication. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) has gained popularity as a student-centered approach to improve fluency through real-life tasks. This study explores how TBLT enhances speaking fluency by engaging learners in meaningful communication. The research highlights the methodology, key findings, and implications for teaching practices

Introduction

Fluency in speaking requires not only a strong grasp of vocabulary and grammar but also the ability to process and produce language quickly and effectively. The communicative approach underlying TBLT aligns with the cognitive processes involved in fluent speech, providing learners with opportunities to practice these skills in a controlled yet realistic environment. Speaking fluency refers to the ability to communicate effectively and naturally without excessive hesitation or errors. Traditional grammar-focused approaches often fail to address the dynamic and spontaneous nature of speaking. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) shifts the focus from accuracy to communication, making it a practical solution for

This paper examines the principles of TBLT and its application to speaking activities. It discusses how task-based instruction promotes fluency by engaging learners in problem-solving, role-plays, and interactive discussions.

Methodology

Tasks were designed to gradually increase in complexity, ranging from simple information exchanges to debates and problem-solving. This scaffolding approach ensured that learners could build confidence while improving their

fluency. Feedback sessions were also conducted after each task, allowing participants to reflect on their performance and identify areas for improvement. The research employs a mixed-method approach, involving both qualitative and quantitative data collection:

1. Participants: 30 intermediate-level English learners aged 18–25.
2. Procedure: Learners were divided into two groups: one receiving traditional instruction and the other using TBLT. Over eight weeks, both groups completed tasks such as role-plays, interviews, and group discussions.
3. Data Collection: Pre- and post-tests were conducted to measure fluency, focusing on speed, accuracy, and coherence.
4. Analysis: Observational data and student feedback were used to evaluate the effectiveness of TBLT.

Findings

Moreover, the TBLT group demonstrated increased interaction and collaboration during group activities, which fostered a sense of community and encouraged more natural conversations. The traditional group, however, reported feeling constrained by the lack of opportunities for spontaneous language use. The results indicated significant improvement in speaking fluency among the TBLT group:

- Increased Speaking Speed: Learners spoke more words per minute with fewer pauses.
- Improved Coherence: Participants demonstrated better organization of ideas.
- Higher Confidence: Students reported feeling more comfortable during spontaneous conversations.

In contrast, the traditional instruction group showed limited progress, often struggling with hesitation and accuracy-focused barriers.

Discussion

The role of the teacher is crucial in facilitating TBLT activities. Teachers must act as guides and provide constructive feedback to help learners overcome challenges. Additionally, incorporating technology, such as digital platforms for task design and delivery, can further enhance the effectiveness of TBLT in modern classrooms.

TBLT encourages learners to focus on meaning rather than form, fostering real-world communication skills. Tasks such as group projects and problem-solving activities mirror authentic language use, making learners more confident and fluent.

However, successful implementation requires careful task design and teacher training. Teachers must balance task complexity to ensure that students remain engaged and challenged without becoming overwhelmed.

Conclusion

By integrating TBLT into language curricula, educators can provide learners with practical tools to navigate real-life communication. This approach not only improves fluency but also promotes critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork skills, making it a holistic method for language education.

Task-Based Language Teaching is an effective approach to developing speaking fluency. By emphasizing real-life communication, it enables learners to overcome speaking barriers and achieve greater fluency. Future research could explore its long-term effects and applicability across different proficiency levels.

References:

1. Ellis, R. (2003). Task-based language learning and teaching. Oxford University Press.
2. Skehan, P. (1996). A framework for the implementation of task-based instruction. *Applied Linguistics*, 17(1), 38-62.
3. Willis, J. (1996). A framework for task-based learning. Longman.
4. Nunan, D. (2004). Task-Based Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press.
5. Richards, J. C. (2008). Teaching listening and speaking: From theory to practice. Cambridge University Press.
6. Bygate, M. (2018). Language learning through task repetition. Benjamins.
7. Prabhu, N. S. (1987). Second language pedagogy. Oxford University Press.
8. Long, M. H. (2015). Second language acquisition and task-based language teaching. Wiley-Blackwell.